

A thienyl-pyridine-based Hantzsch ester fluorescent probe for the selective detection of nitric oxide and its bio-imaging applications

Syed Samim Ali, Ajoy Kumar Pramanik, Sandip Kumar Samanta, Uday Narayan Guria and
Ajit Kumar Mahapatra*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur,
Howrah-711 103, West Bengal, India

E-mail : akmahapatra@chem.iiests.ac.in

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Abstract : A new Hantzsch ester fluorescent probe (TPC) containing thienyl-pyridine group appended to the dihydropyridine ring was synthesized and characterized and successfully applied in the fluorescent sensing nitric oxide (NO) in aqueous solution. The fluorescence of probe TPC shows extremely strong blue fluorescent, while its fluorescence was greatly switched off upon the addition of NO solution and showed high selectivity and sensitivity to NO. The limit of the detection was calculated to be $\sim 0.4 \mu\text{M}$. A reaction mechanism for dihydropyridine with NO is proposed in this study. The probe shows good stability over a broad pH range ($\text{pH} > 4$). The structure of the TPC probe has been established by single-crystal XRD. DFT and TDDFT calculations were done to demonstrate the electronic properties of the probe and the corresponding aromatic product. Moreover, the utility of the TPC probe in detecting NO in live cells has also been demonstrated using Raw 264.7 cells as monitored by fluorescence imaging.

Keywords : Nitric oxide, single crystal X-ray, DFT, live cell imaging.

Introduction

Nitric oxide (NO) is one of the smallest gaseous molecules which exists in the atmosphere. It is a highly reactive and multifunctional free radical, and was primarily accepted as an air pollutants known as nitrogen oxides (NO_x)¹. NO is produced from the reaction of N_2 and O_2 during high-temperature combustion processes in car engines, power plants or industrial processes and naturally by lightning during a thunderstorm. High NO_x levels in the atmosphere can cause serious diseases such as carcinogenesis and asthma². NO is also a ubiquitous bioactive signaling molecule³. Recently, researchers have discovered that NO also serves as an indicator for many biological processes in the human immune system, nervous system, epithelium system and its pivotal role in cardiovascular system⁴. Several analytical methods for NO detection have been developed such as electrophoresis, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) or GC-mass spectroscopies, chemiluminescence and electrochemical methods⁵. In

comparison to these protocols, colorimetric or fluorescence-based techniques present a large number of advantages, such as simple detection *in situ* or at site without any sample pre-treatment or use of low-cost, widely available equipment. Thus, the construction of small fluorescent sensors suitable for specific NO detection in living systems has received great attention. A number of fluorescent probes have been reported to date⁶. The most common approach for NO detection involves the use of *o*-diamino aromatics under aerobic conditions. These molecules react with N_2O_3 (formed from NO and O_2), to yield fluorescent triazole derivatives⁷. Another family of probes, in this case reacting directly with NO, is based on transition-metal complexes⁸. An increasing number of other strategies have been described in the literature⁹.

A widely adopted approach involves a two-component "fluorophore-modulator" strategy for designing reaction-based fluorogenic NO probes. The reaction between *o*-phenylenediaminophenyl and NO is the most

well known and widely used modulating mechanism of fluorogenic NO probes. It is believed that an aromatic vicinal diamine can efficiently quench a fluorophore subunit through the photoinduced electron transfer (PET) mechanism. The reaction of an aromatic vicinal diamine with NO in the presence of oxygen leads to the formation of triazole that blocks the nonradiative PET relaxation pathway and restores fluorescence emission of the fluorophore¹⁰. However, this developed strategy still has its limitations as follows: (i) Self-oxidation-sensitive electron-abundant *o*-phenylenediamine groups makes it easily react with other reactive oxygen/nitrogen species, lighting up its fluorescence and interfering with the sensing process of NO; (ii) oxidized species rather than NO itself are demanded to react with the vicinal aromatic diamines. To solve those problems, our group recently reported a highly selective fluorogenic probe for NO sensing based on the 4-substituted Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines (DHP)¹¹. According to the former work, DHP is not only able to quantitatively react with NO to give the corresponding pyridine, but also exhibits a good selectivity for NO against other interfering reactive oxidative species (ROS), a reaction that is independent of oxygen¹².

Taking the above information into consideration, we report herein the rational design and experimental validation of a highly selective fluorogenic probe for NO sensing based on a fluorescence switching-on-off mechanism. It is known that 1,4-dihydropyridine (Hantzsch ester) is the key switching unit, its oxidation to pyridine by NO would result in the formation of corresponding aromatic pyridine ring. A dramatic electron structure change (from nonaromatic to aromatic) accompanies this chemical transformation, which makes the Hantzsch ester a likely candidate as a pendant group for developing PET based fluorescence NO probes. Herein, we report the PET-based fluorescent NO probe, TPC, for the detection of NO with high selectivity over other reactive oxygen species with high sensitivity for NO.

Results and discussion

The probe molecule, **TPC**, was synthesized via known Hantzsch pyridine synthesis procedure starting

from 6-(2-thienyl)-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (**1**) as shown in Scheme 1. The structure of **TPC** was confirmed by ¹H NMR and LCMS spectra. The molecular structure of **TPC** has been further established on the basis of single-crystal XRD data. Subsequently, we examined their reactivity toward NO through UV-Vis and fluorescence spectra in HEPES buffers (15 mM, pH 7.4, containing 40% DMSO) at 25 °C. Isoamyl nitrite was used as the source of NO, which is commercially available with a half life of 30 min.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions: *Ethylacetoacetate, NH₃ (**1**), reflux for 8 h.

Crystal structure of TPC

The fine and X-ray quality single crystal of pale-yellow colored **TPC** was grown by slow evaporation of the solvent from a solution in MeOH-CH₃CN (1 : 1) at room temperature with ambient condition over a week. The probe crystallizes as monoclinic system with space group P21 and CCDC entry no. 1547182. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters of the probe **TPC** are given in Experimental section. The X-ray bond lengths and angles well reproduced with the standard parameters.

The unit cell structure of **TPC** exhibits a regular twinned aggregation of the same species joined together in some definite mutual orientation. Twinning may occur when a unit cell has higher symmetry than implied by the space group of the crystal structure. The molecular structure constitutes of two moieties i.e. thienyl-pyridine moiety and Hantzsch ester moiety. Now, two planes between the two thienyl-pyridine moieties of the twin are almost parallel to each other having angle of 177.11° and distance of 7.457 Å. Similarly, planes between the two Hantzsch ester moieties of the twin are almost parallel having angle of 177.58° and distance of 2.551 Å.

The crystal structure of **TPC** is stabilized by intermolecular hydrogen bonding which forms a 1-dimen-

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Fig. 1. ORTEP structure of **TPC**, showing 35% thermal ellipsoids probability level for non-H atoms with atom numbering scheme.

sional supramolecular network. Interesting feature of crystal packing (Fig. 2) is the two types of *face-to-face* intermolecular H-bonding [N2–H2····O3] and [N4–H4····O5] with donor–H····Acceptor distance of 2.983(2) and 3.004(4) Å to a series of adjacent parallel unit viewed along b-axis (Fig. 2).

spectra of a mixture of probe **TPC** with different concentrations of NO in aqueous-DMSO solution. When increasing the concentration of NO, a new absorption band at ~338 nm was gradually enhanced, while the intensity of other two bands at ~265 and ~305 nm were decreased correspondingly. The color of the so-

Fig. 2. The crystal packing diagram of **TPC** shows 1-D supramolecular network involving *face-to-face* H····bonding viewed along the b-axis (H atoms not involved are omitted in for clarity).

Spectroscopic properties and response to TPC

The absorption spectra of free probe **TPC** and the colorimetric sensing ability with NO in HEPES buffer (15 mM, pH 7.4, containing 40% DMSO) was monitored at 25 °C and exhibited different bands from 200 to 400 nm. These spectra are typical of an aromatic compound. Fig. 3 shows that the UV-Vis absorption

lution of probe **TPC** was changed from colorless to light yellow. Two clear isosbestic points were observed at ~273 and ~319 nm. This result demonstrates that a complex formation of probe **TPC** with NO is taking place via radical interactions. The formation of these radicals affects the electronic properties of the fluorophore, resulting the change between the non-

Fig. 3. (a) Absorbance spectra of **TPC** ($4 \times 10^{-5} M$) at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 338 \text{ nm}$, upon addition of **NO** ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$) in **DMSO-H₂O** (15.0 mM **HEPES** buffer, 4 : 6 v/v, pH 7.4, at 25 °C). (b) Plot of absorption intensity vs concentration of **NO** (M).

aromatic and the aromatic species. The spectra here are very similar to those of the probe we reported previously. On the account of the quantitatively **NO**-induced conversion of Hantzsch ester into the pyridine form, the change of the fluorescence herein inspired us to utilize the probe **TPC** as effective **NO** fluorescent probe.

To check the fluorescence response of probe **TPC** to **NO**, the fluorescence spectra of **TPC** and its titration experiments upon the addition of various equivalents of **NO** in **HEPES** buffer (50 mM, pH 7.4, containing 40% **DMSO**) was monitored at 25 °C. The

probe **TPC** exhibits strong fluorescence emission at $\sim 439 \text{ nm}$ owing to the inhibition of photoelectron transfer (**PET**) process from the thienyl-pyridine aromatic part to dihydropyridine moiety due to geometrical constrained (orthogonal arrangement), when excited at $\sim 338 \text{ nm}$ in **HEPES** buffer. Titration of probe **TPC** with **NO** results in the decrease of the fluorescence intensity as a function of the added **NO** concentration (Fig. 4) and the intensity saturates at ≥ 3 equiv.

The *switch off* fluorescence emission is expected to the photoelectron transfer (**PET**) upon the aromatization of the Hantzsch ester, which caused the attain-

Fig. 4. (a) Fluorescence spectra of **TPC** ($4 \times 10^{-5} M$) at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 338 \text{ nm}$, upon addition of **NO** ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$) in **DMSO-H₂O** (15.0 mM **HEPES** buffer, 4 : 6 v/v, pH 7.4, at 25 °C). (b) Plot of fluorescence intensity vs concentration of **NO** (M).

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ment of planarity. In addition, a linear relationship between the fluorescent intensity and the concentrations of NO was constructed. Meanwhile, the calculated lowest limit detection (LOD, $3\sigma/\text{slope}$) was determined to be about $0.40 \mu\text{M}$, which is similar with the values in literatures¹³, suggesting that probe TPC is a highly sensitive agent for detecting NO.

In order to check whether probe TPC is sensitive to only NO or even to the other reactive oxygen species (ROS), fluorescence titrations were carried out in the same medium with different ROS, viz. NO, HNO, OH^\bullet , NO_3^- , H_2O_2 , NO_2^- , ClO^- and ONOO^- no sig-

nificant fluorescence change was found in the presence of these ROS (Fig. 5a).

Moreover, the interfering experiment was conducted by adding 10 equiv. of the above mentioned reactive species to the solutions of TPC (Fig. 5b) in the presence of 3.0 equiv. of NO. Noticing that the added interfering species were largely excessive, it demonstrated that TPC can serve as a highly selective fluorescence probe for NO.

Under UV light, the solution of probe TPC is intense blue fluorescent, whereas in the presence of NO

Fig. 5. (a) Fluorescence spectral changes of TPC (4×10^{-5}) in the presence of 10 equiv. of different analytes. (b) Competitive selectivity of TPC (4×10^{-5}) toward NO (3 equiv.) in the presence of other analytes (10 equiv.).

Fig. 6. The visible color (top) and fluorescence changes (bottom) of receptor **TPC** in aq. DMSO (DMSO : H₂O = 4 : 6 v/v, 15 mM HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4) upon addition of various analytes.

non-fluorescent was observed (Fig. 6) and no such fluorescent color change was observed in case of the other ROS. Thus, NO can easily be differentiated by its fluorescent color change from the other ROS.

Next, we studied the influence of pH on the fluorescence of probe **TPC** during NO titration. The titrations carried out at different pH of the medium exhibited no variation in the fluorescence intensity in the pH range 2.0–10.0. These measured results proved that probe **TPC** was a potential fluorometric candidate for monitoring NO in the environment and living cells.

Considering the importance of the responsive time to the analyte for a reactive probe, the time dependent fluorescence spectra were investigated after addition of 3.0 equiv. of NO to the solution of probe **TPC** (Fig. 7). After addition of NO into the solution of

Fig. 7. Change of fluorescence intensity in presence of NO at different pH.

probe **TPC**, the fluorescence emission decreased rapidly, and it became stable in 30 min.

Computational studies

Here NO transformed a nonaromatic species dihydropyridine (**TPC**) derivative to its corresponding aromatic pyridine (**TPC-Ar**) moiety, which makes a dramatic electronic and structural changes occurs in this chemical transformation.

To gain insights into the nature of this fluorescence switching-off mechanism based on NO-induced aromatization of the Hantzsch ester, computational stud-

Fig. 8. Energy minimization structure of (a) **TPC** and (b) **TPC-Ar**.

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ies based on density functional theory (DFT) and time-dependent DFT (TDDFT) were performed at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of the Gaussian 09 program.

Results from calculation revealed that the E_{LUMO} level of the dihydropyridine Hantzsch ester (Fig. 9) was about -1.899 eV, higher than that of the E_{LUMO} level (-2.483 eV) of the thienyl pyridine moiety. Upon NO-induced aromatization of the Hantzsch ester, the E_{LUMO} level (-3.17 eV) of the pyridine was below that of the E_{LUMO} level (-2.483 eV) of the thienyl-pyridine moiety, which drive PET process and therefore turn off fluorescence of the probe.

The TDDFT calculation revealed the absorption bands in the region of λ_{max} , 250–450 nm. The vertical transitions were found to have a good agreement with the experimentally found data.

TDDFT calculations showed absorption band at ~ 357 and ~ 339 nm belonging to the HOMO→LUMO (84.31 %) ($f = 0.1302$) and HOMO→LUMO+5 (74.41 %) ($f = 0.034$) energy states respectively for probe **TPC**.

Bioimaging in living cells

We then assessed the potential utility of **TPC** for the specific imaging of NO in living cells. For this purpose, the cytotoxicity of probe **TPC** toward Raw 264.7 cells were evaluated by using a standard MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay.

The results in Fig. 10e showed that compound **TPC** displayed low cytotoxicity in the adoptive concentration ranges, indicating the high feasibility in biologi-

Fig. 9. Molecular orbital plots for the HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1 of **TPC** and **TPC-Ar**.

Fig. 10. Images of Raw 264.7 cells : (a) bright field, (b) confocal images of Raw 264.7 cells incubated with **TPC** ($20.0 \mu\text{M}$) for 4 h, (c) bright field, (d) confocal images of 264.7 cells incubated with **1** ($20.0 \mu\text{M}$) for 3 h, and then incubated with NO (3 equiv.) for 15 min and (e) MTT assay to determine the cytotoxic effect of **TPC** on Raw 264.7 cells.

cal measurement. Probe **TPC** was then applied for detecting endogenously generated NO by incubating Raw 264.7 cells in the presence or absence of bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS)¹⁴. Raw 264.7 cells were incubated in PBS buffer (pH 7.4) containing 15 μM of the probe **TPC** for 20 min at 37 °C, followed by washing the cells with the same buffer to remove the excess of the probes. At this stage, the fluorescence microscopy image of Raw 264.7 cells displayed intense blue fluorescence. However, upon the addition of isoamyl nitrite (source of NO) into the cells via incubation with LPS solution for 20 min at 37 °C, the cells exhibited non-fluorescent (Fig. 10d). These results demonstrate that the probe **TPC** is capable of detecting NO in living cells.

Conclusion

We have synthesized and characterized thienyl-pyridine-based Hantzsch ester, **TPC** fluorescent probe for detecting nitric oxide (NO) in HEPES buffer medium. The selectivity and sensitivity was demonstrated on the basis of fluorescence, absorption, LC-mass spectrometry, and visual fluorescent color changes. Fluorescence titrations showed the probe is sensitively and linear-dependent to the NO concentration and can be detect up to $\sim 0.4 \mu\text{M}$. The probe displayed a high specificity for NO when compared with other N-, O-sensitive species. NO-induced aromatization of the Hantzsch ester is responsible for the fluorescence change mechanism in the sensing process. The structure of **TPC** has been established by single-crystal XRD. Theoretical calculations were performed to understand the photo-physical behaviors for probe **TPC** and its aromatized compound, and the obtained results also supported the sensing mechanism. The probe **TPC** demonstrated good photophysical stability in the pH range of 4.0–9.0 and low cytotoxicity. The probe was successfully applied in the field of cell imaging for detecting NO in the cell. Strong fluorescent images were observed when Raw cells were incubated with the probe **TPC** alone. However, non-fluorescence was observed in Raw cells in the presence of NO. Further work to improve the sensitivity and put into practical applications is in progress.

Experimental

Chemicals, method and measurements : UV grade dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) was purchased from spectrochem. Isoamyl nitrite was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Pvt. Ltd. (India). Other chemicals were obtained from commercial suppliers and were used without further purification. Mass spectra was carried out using a Waters QTOF Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer. ¹H spectra was recorded on a Bruker 400 MHz instrument. For NMR spectra, DMSO-*d*₆ and CDCl₃ were used as solvent using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm units and 1H–1H and 1H–C coupling constants in Hz. UV spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-530 spectrophotometer. Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model LS 55 spectrophotometer.

Cell culture procedure : Raw 264.7 cell lines were prepared from continuous culture in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, Sigma Chemical Co., St. Louis, MO) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Invitrogen), penicillin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and streptomycin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The Raw 264.7 were acquired from the American Type Culture Collection (Rockville, MD) and maintained in DMEM containing 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum and antibiotics in a CO₂ incubator. At first cells were initially cultivated in 75 cm² polystyrene, filter-capped tissue culture flask in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ and 95% air at 37 °C in CO₂ incubator. When the cells almost reached the logarithmic phase, the cell density was adjusted to 1.0×10^5 per/well in culture media. Then the cells were used to inoculate in a glass bottom dish, with 1.0 mL (1.0×10^4 cells) of cell suspension in each dish. Culture medium was removed just after cell adhesion. The cell layer was rinsed thrice with phosphate buffered saline (PBS), and then used according to the experimental need.

Confocal imaging procedure : For confocal imaging studies Raw 264.7 cell, 1×10^4 cells in 1000 μL of medium, were seeded on sterile 35 mm covered glass bottom, Petridis, culture dish (ibidi GmbH, Germany), and incubated at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator for 10 h. Then cells were washed with 500 μL DMEM and then incubation with (8 μM) isoamyl nitrite dissolved in 500 μL DMEM at 37 °C for 1 h in a CO₂ incubator and analyzed under an Olympus IX81 microscope

equipped with a FV1000 confocal system using 1003 oil immersion Plan Apo (N.A. 1.45) objectives. All images obtained through section scanning were analyzed by Olympus Fluoview (version 3.1a; Tokyo, Japan) with excitation at 338 nm monochromatic laser beam, and emission spectra were integrated over the range 400–650 nm (single channel). The cells were again washed thrice with phosphate buffered saline PBS (pH 7.4) to remove any free isoamyl nitrite and incubated in PBS containing probe **TPC** to a final concentrations of 4.0×10^{-6} M, incubated for 10 min followed by washing with PBS three times to remove excess probe outside the cells and images were captured. The confocal microscope settings for all images, such as scan speed and transmission density were held constant for comparing the relative intensity of intracellular fluorescence.

General computational method : Geometries have been optimized using the B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) level of theory. The geometries are verified as proper minima by frequency calculations. Time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) calculation has also been performed at the same level of theory. All calculations have been carried out using Gaussian 09 program.

Determination of the detection limit : The detection limit was calculated based on the fluorescence titration. The fluorescence emission spectra of **TPC** were measured, and the standard deviation of blank measurements was acquired. To obtain information about the slope, the fluorescence intensity at I_0/I was plotted as a concentration of NO. Then, the detection limit was calculated using the following equation : Detection limit = $3\sigma/k$. In which σ is the standard deviation of 10 blank measurements, k is the slope between the fluorescence intensity versus NO concentration.

General procedure for preparation of solution for UV-Vis titration : A stock solution of the probe **TPC** (4×10^{-5} M) was prepared in DMSO/H₂O (4 : 6 v/v). All experiments were carried out in DMSO/H₂O solution (4 : 6 v/v, 15 mM HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4). Titration experiment was carried out by adding (4×10^{-5} M) solution **TPC** in a quartz optical cell of 1 cm optical path length, and the analyte stock solutions

(4×10^{-4} M) were added into the quartz optical cell slowly by using a micropipet.

General procedure for preparation of solution for fluorescence titration : A stock solution of the probe **TPC** (4×10^{-5} M) was prepared in DMSO/H₂O (4 : 6 v/v). All experiments were carried out in DMSO/H₂O solution (DMSO/H₂O = 4 : 6 v/v, 15 mM HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4). Titration experiment was carried out by adding (4×10^{-5} M) solution **TPC** in a quartz optical cell of 1 cm optical path length, and the analyte stock solutions (4×10^{-4} M) were added into the quartz optical cell slowly by using a micropipet. In selectivity experiments, the test samples were prepared by placing appropriate amounts of the analyte, stock into 2 mL of solution of probes (4×10^{-5} M).

Synthesis of TPC : 6-(2-Thienyl)-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (**1**) (0.3 g, 1.58 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (1.1 g, 9.2 mmol) and ammonia solution (0.2 g, 9.2 mmol) were dissolved in 10 ml ethanol and refluxed for 10 h. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction mixture was concentrated *in vacuo* to get crude product which was purified by column chromatography using ethyl acetate in hexane (1 : 9) and finally get pure compound **TPC**. Yellow solid, (260 mg, 44%), m.p. 190–195 °C, MS (LCMS) : (*m/z*, %) : 413.2 [(**TPC** + H⁺), 100 %]; Calculated for C₁₂H₂₄N₂O₄S : 412.15. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 400 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.47 (2H, m), 7.38 (1H, d, *J*=7.6 Hz), 7.26 (1H, t *J*=13.16), 7.04 (2H, m), 5.70 (1H, s), 5.12 (1H, s), 4.11 (4H, m), 2.35 (6H, s), 1.23 (6H, m).

X-Ray crystal structure determination

The X-ray quality single crystal of **TPC** was grown by slow diffusion in MeOH-CH₃CN (1 : 1) under ambient condition for a week. Block shaped pale-yellow crystal of dimension 0.18 × 0.14 × 0.09 mm. Unit cell parameters were determined from least-squares method with the data in the range of $-9 \leq h \leq 9$, $-22 \leq k \leq 22$, $-23 \leq l \leq 23$ and angle varies $1.197 < \theta < 28.85^\circ$. Other unit cell parameters are $a = 7.3479(6)$, $b = 16.3371(13)$, $c = 17.2146(12)$ (Å) and $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 98.693(4)$. Out of total reflections 68151 unique data 6125 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) were used for structure determination.

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